

ICP-AES determination of rare earth elements in coal fly ash samples of thermal power stations : assessment of possible recovery and environmental impact of rare earth elements

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Abstract : Accurate determination of rare earth elements (REEs) in coal ashes of thermal power plants is important in the current scenario due to its (i) economic value, and (ii) the pollution caused if they are released in to the environment. Their toxicity to living organisms now gaining importance in international community, and some investigation shows it causes retardation in plant growth. In coal based thermal power stations huge quantity of coal is used annually as a fuel and lakhs of tones of waste is generated in the form of ashes. Therefore, studies were carried out on three aspects (i) fairly rapid and accurate ICP-AES determination of REEs in coal fly ash samples using standard addition technique, (ii) a preliminary acid leaching studies on coal ashes received from three different coal fired thermal power stations using hydrochloric acid at pH 1 and 2, and quantify the REEs leached, and (iii) probable economic recovery of REEs using di-(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid solvent extraction process or precipitation as REEs hydroxides using dilute ammonia solution. The standard addition method of REEs determination using ICP-AES gives fairly accurate and reproducible values, besides the analysis is fast as compared to the ion exchange separation of REEs followed by the ICP-AES determination.

Keywords : Coal fly ash, REEs, ICP-AES determination, REEs recovery, di-(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid.

Introduction

Accurate determination of rare earth elements (REEs) [as per classification schemes recognized by IUPAC, yttrium and Sc are combined with lanthanides to form the rare earth elements] in coal ashes of thermal power plants is of important in the current scenario. The wide spread applications of REEs in industry such as catalysts, magnetic materials and in electronics increasing¹. The coal ashes from super thermal power stations can also be considered as an alternate source materials for REEs. Moreover, if they are not removed from coal ashes along with other heavy metals, in future, they may cause environmental pollution particularly the soil, river, streams and ground water of adjoining areas of coal ash landfills, if these landfills are comes in contact with the acidic mine water of sulphide bearing minerals like pyrite^{2,3}. Their toxicity to living organisms was not explored earlier, now gaining importance in international community, and some investigation shows it causes retardation in plant growth⁴. In the earth crust they are usually associated with igneous

and sedimentary rocks as monazite, xenotime, and zircon minerals which are refractory in nature. Therefore, they are not liberated from the mineral matrix under normal weathering conditions. During the coal formation process from vegetation which happened over a long period of time some amount of silicate minerals along with the above REEs bearing minerals intrudes in the cleavages, fractures and vacant spaces during the sedimentation process. Though their concentration as such in coal is less, but when coal is used as fuel, in the ash these elements get enriched by a factor of ten or more depending on matrix disintegration due to the very high temperature for a long residence time in the hearth, the damage to the crystal lattice therein, the quality of coal and environment of coal sedimentation process.

Our laboratory has received coal ash samples for the analysis of uranium and REEs from four different thermal Power Stations in India, such as Neyveli Thermal Power Station, Cuddalore, Tamilnadu, Thermal Power Station at Ramagundam, Karimnagar, Andhra Pradesh,

Singrauli Super Thermal Power Station at Shakti Nagar, Sonbhadra, Uttar Pradesh and Surat Thermal Power Station at Nani Naroli, Gujarat. The latter three power stations are using sub bituminous or bituminous types coal. During the course of studies it was observed that there were vast variations in REEs content in these coal ashes. It was also observed that unlike the minerals like monazite, xenotime and zircon⁵ these coal ash residues release REEs and other heavy elements under mild acid treatments. Therefore, acid leaching studies on coal ash samples were carried at pH around 1 or above for period of six hours contact time. If the REEs concentrations are fairly good in coal ash, and easily leachable in nature, they can be used as additional source for these much demanded elements, which will reduce the inevitable environmental pollution considerably.

Experimental

Instrument :

A Jobin Yvon model Ultima II sequential ICP-OES from M/s Jobin Yvon, France was used for emission measurements. The instrumental parameters used are given in Table 1. Two replicate measurements were made for each element. A built in auto background correction software was used. The emission lines (λ in nm) and the operating conditions used for the REE measurements are those as mentioned by the manufacturer.

Reagents and chemicals :

All reagents and chemicals used were of Analytical or Guaranteed Reagent grade, and double distilled water was used throughout the study.

Preparation of standards :

A stock solution of 1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ each was prepared from the high purity (>99.99%) oxides/salts of lanthanides were prepared employing suitable acid digestion procedure⁶. Working standard solutions for instrumental calibration were prepared by serial dilution of stock standard solution. A combined reference solutions were prepared in 5% HCl containing (a) 0.5 to 5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ containing La, Ce, Nd, Gd, Dy, 0.1–2 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ Eu, Yb, Lu, Y and Sc; (b) 0.2–2 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ containing Pr, Sm, Tb, Ho, Er and Tm, respectively.

Sample dissolution :

A 0.500 g coal ash sample (–200 mesh size) was taken in a 30 ml capacity platinum crucible and ignited in a muffle furnace at 850 °C for two hours to remove any residual unburned carbon. It was treated twice with 5 ml each of hydrofluoric and nitric acid on a boiling water bath to dryness, subsequently with 5 ml nitric acid alone to dryness. The content was digested with dilute nitric acid and transferred in to a 50 ml flask maintaining 5% nitric acid.

Table 1. A comparison of REEs results obtained by ICP-AES using (i) direct determination, (ii) standard addition method and (iii) after the ion exchange separation methods in different fly ash samples

	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu	Y	Sc
RF-Direct	78	122	16	73	13	3.0	21	<3	9	<3	8	<3	4.0	0.7	46	23
RF-Std. Add	83	130	18	80	15	3.2	22	<3	10	<3	8	<3	4.5	0.8	49	25
RF-IE	81	127	17	80	15	3.3	23	<3	10	<3	8	<3	4.5	0.8	50	–
SNF-Direct	138	243	29	122	23	5.0	35	3	15	3	11	<3	6.0	1.0	89	81
SNF-Std. Add	145	255	31	128	25	5.4	37	3	16	3	12	<3	6.5	1.1	95	89
SNF-IE	143	250	32	130	26	5.4	38	3	16	3	12	<3	6.4	1.0	94	–
NLPS-Direct	260	587	92	515	102	30	103	14	72	<3	38	<3	26	5.1	311	46
NLPS-Std. Add	275	615	97	540	110	33	110	15	78	3	41	<3	28	5.5	320	48
NLPS-IE	271	610	95	538	112	35	120	17	79	3	41	<3	27	5.4	322	–
SLPF-Direct	25	46	<10	42	<10	2.0	25	3	8	<3	9	<3	4.0	2.1	39	35
SLPF-Std. Add	28	49	<10	45	<10	2.2	27	3	9	<3	10	<3	4.3	2.3	42	41
SLPF-IE	27	47	<10	45	<10	2.1	28	3	9	<3	11	<3	4.3	2.3	42	–

RF – Fly ashes of Thermal Power Station at Ramagundam, SNF – Singrauli Super Thermal Power Station fly ash, NLPS – Neyveli Thermal Power Station fly ash, SLPF – Surat Thermal Power Station fly ash.

Std. Add is standard addition method.

IE is separation of REEs by cation exchange method (Ref. 7).

ICP-AES determination of the REEs :

From the stock solution 8 ml aliquot each was transferred into two 10 ml volumetric flasks. To one flask 1 ml of lanthanides stock solution containing 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ Ce, La, Nd, Gd and Dy, 5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ each of Pr, Sm, Tb, Ho, Tm and 2 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ each of Eu, Yb, Lu, Y and Sc was added and both flasks were diluted to the mark. To a third 10 ml flask 1 ml of the above REE stock solution was taken and diluted the mark. The emission measurements of REEs of these solutions were carried out in sequence (first sample solution alone, second sample solution doped with REE and third doped amount of REE alone) were carried out. On the basis of the recovery of known amount of REEs added, the amount of REE present in the sample was calculated. The results obtained are shown in Table 1 along with REEs results after the ion-exchange separation⁷. The concentration of the analyte was determined as per following equation :

$$\frac{\text{Net intensity counts of standard alone} \times \text{Net intensity counts of analyte in the sample} \times \text{Sample dilution factor}}{\text{Net intensity counts of doped standard in sample matrix}}$$

Net intensity counts of doped standard in sample matrix

Coal fly ash acid leaching studies :

A 0.250 g sample (-200 mesh size) was taken in a stoppered conical flask and treated with 25 ml each dilute hydrochloric acid solution maintained at pH 1 and 2 at room temperature for about six hours with occasional swirling. It was filtered and the filtrate was analysed for REEs. The results obtained are shown in Table 2.

REE recovery using HDEHP and hydroxide precipitation :

About 1.00 g coal fly ash samples were treated with 50 ml of 0.1 M HCl as above. The filtered solution pH was adjusted around 2 by adding few drops of dilute ammonia solution and mixed with 5 mg ascorbic acid; the REEs were extracted with 10% (v/v) DEHPA in kerosene previously washed with 6 M HCl and equilibrated with 0.1 M HCl. The extracted REEs were stripped twice using 10 ml each 4 M HCl. The aqueous strip was evaporated dryness with 5 ml nitric acid and 1 ml perchloric acid on a hot plate and diluted to 50 ml maintaining 5% HCl for ICP-AES measurement. The extractant can be reused several times.

Hydroxide precipitation of REEs :

The acid leached REEs were precipitated as hydroxides using dilute ammonia solution by raising the pH around 10. A small amount of iron leached from the coal fly ash acts as carrier.

Results and discussion*ICP-AES determination of REEs :*

Direct determination of REEs in the coal ash sample solution gave 5 to 10% lower values as compared to the ICP-AES values after ion exchange separation of REEs. Spectral interference studies were carried out independently using 500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of each Al and Fe, 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ each of Ca and Mg on each individual REEs having 2 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations, using the lines stated in the experimental portion. The result shows no significant direct spectral overlap, except on Yb and Lu by iron above 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Spectral interference of Fe was more on Lu as

Table 2. A comparative hydrochloric acid leaching studies of REEs on three thermal power stations coal ash samples

	SN-Fly ash				NLP-Fly ash			RAM-Fly ash			
	Total	0.5 M	pH ~1	pH ~2	Total	pH ~1	pH ~2	Total	0.5 M	pH ~1	pH ~2
La	145	30	12	5	275	255	20	83	10	8	3
Ce	255	52	19	7	615	505	35	130	18	12	6
Eu	5.4	1.2	0.4	<1	33	24	1.3	3.2	0.4	0.4	<1
Gd	37	6	4	3	110	76	6	22	4	4	3
Yb	6.5	1.8	0.9	<0.5	26	24	1	4.5	0.4	0.9	<0.5
Lu	1.1	0.4	<1	<0.5	5.1	4	<1	0.8	0.4	<1	<0.5
Y	95	23	16	6	311	307	20	49	8	16	2
Sc	89	14	10	2	46	36	8	25	4	10	<1

SN - Singrauli Super Thermal Power Station, NLP - Neyveli Thermal Power Station, RAM - Thermal Power Station at Ramagundam.

compared to Yb. It was corrected mathematically, and also the measurement of Lu and Yb were carried out after the selective separation of REEs using MIBK solvent extraction in 6 M hydrochloric acid medium. The corrected values for Yb and Lu are given in Tables 1 and 2. The non-spectral interferences caused by the associated matrix elements slightly reduced the analyte emission intensity, varying from 5 to 10% due to the increased salt load in the plasma and emission lines used for the measurement. This suppression could not overcome completely even using 1200 W forward plasma power. Therefore, under the same matrix elements concentrations, the net emission intensity of the doped REEs were calculated and corresponding correction was applied to sample analyte signal. The values obtained by this method are near to the values of REEs obtained after the ion exchange separation. The ICP-AES analysis results obtained on three coal fly ash samples directly, after standard addition and after the selective separation REEs are given in Table 1, it shows that values obtained by the standard addition method is fairly accurate. The reproducibility was also checked by repeated analysis of the same sample, and the %RSD obtained is 3 to 5% under the concentration levels of REEs shown in Table 1.

Coal fly ash acid leaching :

In the earth crust REEs are normally associated in the refractory minerals like monazite, xenotime, and zircon. These minerals are not disintegrated under the normal weathering condition, and also with mild mineral acid concentrations studied. However, when these minerals are burned in the furnace in a reducing atmosphere for a long period, depend upon its crystal lattice energy, mineral lattice undergoes varying rate of disintegration facilitating the liberation of REEs under mild acid condition. Further, it was observed that leaching of REEs from fly ashes varies from thermal power stations depends on the type of coal originated from different areas. The studies carried out on fly ashes obtained three different thermal power stations are given in Table 2. It indicates that mineralogy plays an important role in releasing the REEs. Fairly good amount of leaching was observed in Neyveli Power Station coal fly ashes wherein lignite is used as the fuel. The REEs data indicates probable association due to monazite (LREE rich) and zircon which contains more Y and Sc as compared to monazite. Since lignite is the

younger form in the sedimentation process the amount of impurities associated are also more. Both Singrauli and Ramagundam Thermal Power Station coal fly ash samples, the REEs contents are relatively less as compared to fly ashes of Neyveli Thermal Power Station. Their acid leachability were also less, it also shows relatively higher values for Y and Sc as compared to the normal monazite mineral indicating the presence of zircon also the sources for REEs contents.

Therefore, the preliminary studies carried out in the laboratory for a very short contact period with dilute hydrochloric acid shows the release of REEs. In reality these coal fly ashes are going to be in contact with the waters of different pH for a very long period under heat and pressure which will further facilitate the release of these elements.

Recovery of REEs from the acid leach liquor :

DEHPA is a widely used reagent for the solvent extraction for REEs, and under varying pH its selectivity shows variations with respect to their ionic radii of the REEs. The REEs leached at pH 1 was quantitatively extracted at pH around 2 using 10% (v/v) DEHPA in kerosene. The extracted metal ions are back extracted with 4 M HCl. However, the recovery of Tm, Yb and Lu were less (90 to 80% recovery) due to their small ionic radii, and Sc could be stripped only partially (<20%). Therefore, after three batches of extraction and back extraction the residual Tm, Yb, Lu and Sc in the organic phase were stripped using 0.1 M ammonium bi-fluoride solution 10 ml each for three tones. A comparison of the amount of REEs present in the leach liquor and the quantity recovered are fairly good to be used commercially for its recovery.

The REEs forms insoluble hydroxides, and at trace levels they precipitate quantitatively with ferric hydroxide. During the acid leaching process small amount of iron is also leached along with the REEs. Therefore, the pH of the solution was raised to around ten to quantitatively precipitate all the REEs and filtered. The iron content in the REEs fraction can further be removed by suitable solvent extraction process. The recovery of REEs obtained by this method was also >95% of the REEs present in the leach liquor.

Conclusions

It has been observed that ICP-AES determination of REEs in coal fly ash samples after the selective separation to avoid both spectral and non-spectral interferences is recommended, it is time consuming and standard addition method gave fairly good value, and it is comparable with the values obtained after the ion exchange separation of REEs. Dilute hydrochloric acid leaching studies on fly ashes indicates the release of REEs ions. In order to avoid the pollution of land, soil, rivers and ground water in future due to the landfills of coal ashes, possible low cost leaching and extraction of REEs are also recommended.

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